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Communication Plan

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Abstract	The current document is the Communication Plan of the UNITE.H2020 project. The aim of the Communication Plan is to describe the strategic communication of the project, in order to achieve a strong and impactful visibility of Unite!.

History of changes

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Abbreviation list

EC – European Commission

KLO – Key Liaison Officer

KPI – Key Performance Indicator

SSMM – Social Media

SCT- Strategic Communication Team

WP/WPC – Work Package/Work Package Coordinator

TF/TFC - Task Force/ Task Force Coordinator

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1. UNITE.H2020 background

UNITE.H2020 is one of the projects of the **Unite! alliance** which originated from the [CLUSTER](#) network of **seven partners** cooperating on different aspects of **higher education, research, innovation and social responsibility**. The seven Unite! partners are [Technical University of Darmstadt](#) (coordinator of the Unite! alliance), [Aalto University](#), [Grenoble INP graduate schools of engineering and management](#), [University Grenoble Alpes](#), [KTH Royal Institute of Technology](#), [Politecnico di Torino](#), [Universidade de Lisboa](#) and [Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya - BarcelonaTech](#). It will receive up to EUR 2 million from the Horizon 2020 programme for the three-year-long pilot phase. This funding complements the EUR 5 million granted to the alliance from the Erasmus+ programme and the additional funds received by several Ministries -such as the Italian Ministry of University and Research (MUR).

Unite! has been firstly selected in June 2019 for a three-year pilot project within the **Erasmus+ programme** of the European Commission, to settle the foundations of Unite! as a **European University alliance**. Unite! is one of the first **17 alliances** of the European Universities Initiative. It consists of bottom-up networks of universities across the EU which will enable students to obtain a degree by combining studies in several EU countries and contribute to the international competitiveness of European universities. Their potential is to significantly enhance mobility and foster high quality and excellence in education and research, by strengthening the link between teaching, research and innovation and knowledge transfer, by demonstrating the benefits of multilingual learning, the recognition of qualifications and by developing joint education and research programmes and projects. European Universities will play a flagship role in the creation of a European Education Area as a whole. Unite! will promote science, technology and engineering education on a multidisciplinary, multicultural and multilingual European campus embedded in fluid regional ecosystems, to provide skills for and shape the mind-sets of a new generation of European and global citizens.

The alliance is committed to an ethical, safe and sustainable use of technology, in line with fair and open science to generate innovative, feasible and effective solutions to global challenges. The alliance also hosts some of the most active entrepreneurial ecosystems, generating start-up activities and innovations with a marked societal impact across Europe and the world. It is thus ideally equipped to address major global challenges. The development of new structures, programmes, initiatives and ideas will focus on three strongly transversal and multidisciplinary topics: **Energy, Artificial intelligence and Industry 4.0**. All Unite! universities have capable research groups and share high-level research and teaching activities in these fields, which have a great technological and societal relevance. This makes this choice an excellent test bed for collaboration opportunities of high general interest. Beyond these topics, Unite! understands itself as creating structures to enable bottom-up approaches, shaped by the contributions of students and staff. Unite! is born with the ambition of becoming a stable alliance in the future, eager to fulfil the long-term vision outlined above. To make this possible, the first pilot project began in 2019 and will be enriched by other projects; it is expected to continue until 2022 and further with the implementation phase (2022-2025), until the full consolidation of the Unite! Alliance.

Within the Unite! alliance framework, the **UNITE.H2020** project, involving the seven universities of the Unite! Alliance and coordinated by **Politecnico di Torino**, has been conceived with the aim of developing, in synergy with the educational dimension of the alliance, an integrated, shared and long-term research and innovation (R&I) strategy. It is financed by the EC for **period 2021-23** and it will address the 2030 vision on the future of universities by developing, together with its educational dimension, the field of R&I in Europe. Within the three years of the Unite.H2020 project, a series of **pilot initiatives** will be carried out in the fields of Energy, Artificial Intelligence and Industry 4.0. The overall aim of the project will be therefore to produce tangible results towards the **institutional transformation of our Universities** and the identification of **good practices for the modernization of Research & Innovation (R&I)**. In the 3 years period the project will (i) Develop a common R&I 2030 agenda, emphasizing the common DNA of the partners and shared vocation to address major societal challenges; (ii) Implement policies to strengthen our R&I human capital by, e.g., new career development initiatives; (iii) Identify policies to share our research infrastructures (RIs) supported by, e.g., experimental tests of previously developed guidelines on a selection of RIs; (iv) Reinforce cooperation with non-academic R&I players by, e.g. developing a network of Grant Offices & TTOs; (v) Mainstream our comprehensive Open Science practices based on, e.g. a detailed experimental analysis

on the approach of our R&I groups to OS; (vi) Involve citizens, civil society and public authorities in R&I; (vii) Strengthen relations with other alliances for joint synergies/complementarities.

2. Communication strategy

In order to clarify some basic concepts, we hereby present an extract from the [H2020 funding guide](#) “Making the most of your H2020”

Horizon 2020 programme places a strong focus on activities which demonstrate and maximise the societal and economic impact of Research & Innovation (R&I) funding. Communication activities to promote the project itself and its success, as well as the dissemination and exploitation of results are thus key components of every Horizon 2020 project. Their successful implementation will bring EU-funded research and its results to the attention of multiple audiences, thus helping to drive competitiveness and growth in Europe and address societal challenges.

Dissemination is the public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium. Dissemination activities should aim to enable others to use and take up results, thus maximising the impact of EU-funded research. It is a planned process of providing information on the results of programmes and initiatives to key actors. It occurs as and when the result of programmes and initiatives become available. In terms of the Horizon 2020 Programme this involves spreading the word about the project successes and outcomes as far as possible to possible users. Making others aware of the project will impact on other organisations in the future and will contribute to raising the profile of the organisation carrying out the project. To effectively disseminate results, an appropriate process at the beginning of the project needs to be designed. This should cover why, what, how, when, to whom and where disseminating results will take place, both during and after the funding period.

Communication is a broader concept. It is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. It takes care of information and promotion activities to raise awareness and enhance the visibility of the project's activities in addition to the dissemination and exploitation of the project results. However, very often it is difficult to make a clear distinction between these areas. For this reason, planning an overall strategy framework covering both fields can be a more efficient way to make the most of the available resources.

2.1 Main objectives

The purpose of the Communication Plan is to create a strong and impactful **visibility for UNITE.H2020** at a European, national and regional level, as well as within the partner universities and their global networks. The actions of this plan will be strategic and targeted measures for promoting the project itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public. Communication will be seamlessly linked to the outcomes of all work packages in order to support the dissemination and to ensure the broadest possible awareness of all stakeholders of upcoming, ongoing activities and outcomes. The dissemination and exploitation of results can help to maximize the effect of the activities being developed so that they will impact on the stakeholders for years to come. Moreover, this Communication plan will contribute to the sustainable and long-term activities that will be developed by the Strategic Communication Team (SCT), composed by representatives from both Unite! Erasmus+ (TF10) and UNITE.H2020 (WP9) projects and coordinating the communication teams of all partners involved in both Unite! Erasmus+ project and UNITE.H2020, in order to ensure a continuum of

dissemination also beyond 2025. The ambition is, through feedbacks, iteration and interventions, to generate a communication platform to answer to the needs of all key stakeholders.

The main objectives of this communication plan will be to:

- Provide universally comprehensible information to the public and mass media on the project goals and results.
- Increase the visibility of Horizon 2020 and the project's contribution to create the university of the future.
- Promote the institutional change carried out within the partner universities for a better quality and competitiveness of European higher education.
- Engage in a two-way dialogue and receive feedbacks from the higher education ecosystem.
- Influence the attitudes of universities governing bodies about the project's contribution to meeting the societal challenges.
- Reach, as a bottom-up network, both the communities of the partner universities and the interested audiences of the quadruple helix with the Unite! Message.
- Spread the role of the alliance as a positive contributor to the principles of Open Science in the framework of the SDGs, through the focus areas of Unite!, namely Energy, Artificial Intelligence, and Industry 4.0 as well as other fields that may emerge from the different WPs as they evolve.
- Create communication models that facilitate the involvement of citizens and society that at the same time can be the basis to share good practices with other European University alliances.

Co-creation is a key aspect of the UNITE.H2020 project and its communication. The SCT will be encouraged to actively contribute by:

- Identifying and informing about communication/dissemination activities (e.g. events, publications, etc.).
- Sharing the contents of their respective work packages such as materials for press releases, presentations, etc.
- Using their network to support the communication/dissemination of project information.
- Presenting UNITE.H2020 and the Unite! alliance at relevant conferences, workshops and other events.
- Helping to promote UNITE.H2020, in particular engaging key stakeholders to act as multipliers and to motivate participants.

2.2 Action lines

The strategy of the communication plan is conceived in four main lines of action:

- Align the existing Unite! alliance project identity (visual identity, website, social networks) with the specific UNITE.H2020 elements.
- Communicate project's achievements to the broadest public through materials adapted to the achieved results (brochures, videos, etc.).
- Consolidate the project's outcomes for communication inside the community of partner universities and to the broad public.
- Monitor and evaluate the communication results and sustainability measures.

The objective is to create a coherent and meaningful narrative that shows the extent and impact of the UNITE.H2020 project within the Unite! alliance, thanks to innovation embracing both academia and research. The cooperation and continuous iteration within the Unite! community will be core to define a harmonic communication. The principles of Open Science and Open Innovation as well as SDGs, will permeate the communication strategy exactly as in the whole project.

2.3 Visual identity

2.3.1 Brand statement

The identity of UNITE.H2020 is in line with the identity of the Unite! Alliance, that is based on the transformative project nature, Unite! brand builds up on the capacities and possibilities of the individual identities of a group of universities with a long history of cooperation. This fact is especially relevant for the development of a brand that is being shaped by an alliance with multiple projects. The brand and all Unite! initiatives should reflect each other and will be recognized through Unite! logo and graphic identity, by embracing the unified communication style established in the Unite! alliance.

2.3.2 The Unite! logo

It consists of the word mark, composite mark, typography and the colours defined for Unite!. A brand book is available for the different uses of the logo. The Unite! logo and new colours have been voted by all partners, as well as Unite! with a capitalised first letter and with the exclamation mark as the proper name of the alliance.

2.3.3 Brand cohabitation: Unite! and the member universities

Brand cohabitation is a key element in the development of Unite! alliance and thus UNITE.H2020 project will be aligned accordingly. The basis of brand cohabitation is the respect and adaptation to the identity and graphic standards of each university (see table below). Consequently, it is proposed a **triple representation** of the brand identity of UNITE.H2020:

- a. Unite! including all member universities' logos: of compulsory use in all UNITE.H2020 project materials, at least once. This allows an emphasis on the alliance-component of the project. We propose three levels of visual prominence:
 - Unite! alliance logo
 - Partner logos.
 - Other logos (collaborators, funding, etc.) (see 3.1.5. Other logos).
- b. UNITE.H2020 as a stand-alone logo: the Unite! logo represents the project.
- c. H2020 funding acknowledgement logo

Logo	Name	Acronym and/or short name	Brand (internal repository)
	Politecnico di Torino	PoliTO	https://ushare.unite-university.eu/tf-10-dissemination/documents/logos-branding-book-partners-logos/polito-logo-and-branding-book#/
	Aalto University	Aalto	https://ushare.unite-university.eu/tf-10-dissemination/documents/04-work-in-progress/partners-visual-identity/aalto-university-brand-library

	Grenoble INP graduate schools of engineering and management, University Grenoble Alpes	Grenoble INP-UGA	https://ushare.unite-university.eu/tf-10-dissemination/documents/logos-branding-book-partners-logos/grenoble-logo-brandbook-and-photos#/
	KTH Royal Institute of Technology	KTH	https://ushare.unite-university.eu/tf-10-dissemination/documents/logos-branding-book-partners-logos/kth-royal-institute-of-technology-1.docx/view#/
	Technical University of Darmstadt	TUDa	https://www.intern.tu-darmstadt.de/media/medien_stabsstelle_km/services/medien_cd/das_bild_der_tu_darmstadt.pdf
	Universidade de Lisboa	ULisboa	https://ushare.unite-university.eu/tf-10-dissemination/documents/logos-branding-book-partners-logos/ulisboa-for-unite-1.docx/view#/
	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya – BarcelonaTech (UPC)	UPC	https://ushare.unite-university.eu/tf-10-dissemination/documents/logos-branding-book-partners-logos/upc-branding-book-unite.docx/view#/

*The English name will be used for all Unite! communications and it must be used the first time an organization is mentioned. After that, the acronym or short version might be used.

2.4 Target audience, engagement objectives and goals

The Unite! alliance is a complex network, which translates into a complex audience matrix. The UNITE.H2020 target audience is thus part of the broad framework of the Unite! alliance which also includes the Unite!E+ project. The collaboration with other WPs in the project (mainly WP2, WP4 and WP7) will help define the most appropriate target audiences both for communication and dissemination, their level of engagement with the alliance and its activities as well as the better channel, event and material to reach them.

2.4.1 Audience description, involvement and goals

The UNITE.H2020 target audience belongs to the three main ecosystems of stakeholders defined within the internal Communication Plan of Unite! alliance with specific features and goals pointed out in the following description. The summary of coordination is as follows:

- The secretariat is responsible for internal communication to the Unite! Ecosystem.
- The SCT is responsible for communication coordination, brand management, Unite! wide external communication channels, templates and strategic communication support.
- All work packages are responsible for communicating their activities to their target groups. These activities should be coordinated with the SCT and adhere to communication principles in the communication strategy, guidelines and recommendations from the SCT.

- Partner universities are responsible for communicating Unite! actions within their universities, and each partner coordinates how, when and where information will be promoted.

- **Unite! Ecosystem (Unite! alliance, Unite! E+ and UNITE.H2020)**

The **internal communication** of Unite! alliance is coordinated by the Unite! secretariat, located at TU Darmstadt, which in this project will act in coordination with the UNITE.H2020 management team in PoliTO. The communication between the project managers and staff establishes the first level of internal communication of the alliance. It is considered strategic communication, especially because it is the force that constitutes the identity of Unite! alliance. The management of this communication has different layers, which may overlap in some cases:

- **From an alliance perspective:** UNITE.H2020 and Unite! E+ communication at a general level, across universities.
- **From a Partner-university perspective:** the projects team of each partner university across WPs.
- **From a Work-Package/Task-Force perspective,** which gathers teams with a common objective across universities.
- **From a Role perspective,** also a transversal layer of communication. It is important to define the following main roles within Unite! alliance:
 - **Key Liaison Officer (KLO):** it is the highest representative of each university in Unite! alliance. He/she is in direct contact with the management team and with the rest of the KLOs. Organize the projects internally at each university. He/she is therefore a key figure for correct and fluid communication at Unite!. All KLOs meet periodically with the management team.
 - **UNITE.H2020 WP Leaders** and Unite!E+ Task Force Coordinator (TFC): as its name indicates, it is the person responsible for coordinating each of the WPs. He/she is in contact with the management team and also with the KLOs
 - **SCT Contact Person per partner:** a strategic figure within UNITE.H2020 WP9 and Unite! E+ TF10 that aims at linking SCT closely to each partner university. They have a double key role: first, connecting with other WP leaders and TFs within their universities, and second, helping WP9 and TF10 take advantage of the existing teams, resources and channels within each partner university.

The Unite! ecosystem is the audience group which is composed of the teams involved in management, governance and projects activities. They are the main **driving agents** of the **UNITE.H2020 and Unite!E+ projects within the partner universities.**

Specific goal: set up the basis for the interaction and cooperation among partner universities, guarantee a fluid interaction, share and disseminate results.

- **Partners' ecosystem**

It includes all communities in the partner universities that can benefit from the Unite! alliance activities but that do not work directly in the alliance.

Administrative staff (Grant offices, Technology Transfer Offices experts and IT services)

Unite! activities and communication will be carried out with the support of local administrative and technical staff of each university, as well as its support services. Their implication is invaluable to build Unite! and integrate the brand at a local level.

For this audience, the figures of KLOs, WP leaders/TFCs and WP9/TF10 Contact person per partner will be key to achieve proper visibility within each partner universities. Moreover, for **UNITE.H2020 it will be fundamental to actively engage mainly the Research Grant Office and the Technology Transfer Office administrative staff for the creation of a network of Research & Innovation**

Services defined in WP2 as well as for Research and Infrastructure mapping and sharing guidelines foreseen in WP3.

Specific goal: inform them of what UNITE.H2020 and Unite! E+ are, inform the staff of their involvement, emphasise the benefits and impact the projects will have in their university and within the European higher-education landscape.

Academic staff

This audience group gathers key roles in high education and research, including researchers, teachers, PhDs and students in representative positions. They are a very relevant target of UNITE.H2020 and Unite! E+, not only because they are potential ambassadors for promoting engagement and disseminating and communicating the projects, but also because they have a key role in the development and success of the different products of Unite! projects. For this audience, the figures of KLOs, WPLeaders/TFCs and WP9/TF10 Contact person per partner will be key to achieve proper visibility within each partner universities.

Specific goal: emphasise what UNITE.H2020 and Unite! E+ might offer them to promote engagement, emphasise their key role in the co-creation of different products of the projects.

Alumni

Unite! Alumni include those who graduate and have been involved in Unite! E+ at any level (activities, Dialogue, etc.). They will be an invaluable resource for the communication & dissemination of Unite! E+ and also for UNITE.H2020, their action, outcomes and impacts at all levels. They are important agents for change and will be able to contribute to the peer-to-peer communication between students (as recent graduates) as well as to collaborate through their professional networks.

Specific goal: engage our students to be strongly committed to Unite! alliance after graduation, also considering their potential involvement in the UNITE.H2020 R&I activities as researchers. The Alumni Ambassadors programme of the Unite! E+ project will also be a communication and dissemination resource for UNITE.H2020, since it will enable the creation of a network of students trained to disseminate and promote the institutions abroad, contributing for the increasing of mobility and cross-institutional collaboration by 2025.

Undergraduate, master and PhD students

The students are the front line in the co-creation, through the Unite! E+, of a European University. For UNITE.H2020 they are the target groups to be engaged in communication activities in order to make them aware of the institutional change the project is contributing to create also in the R&I aspects of the University of the future they can look for. As a bottom-up network, they are both beneficiaries and active agents in shaping the alliance, which make them key to the development and success of Unite!. For UNITE.H2020 in particular they could be the next generation of researchers trained thanks to the new University model.

Specific goal: inform them of what UNITE.H2020 and Unite!E+ are, foster a sense of Unite! belonging, emphasise the benefits and impact Unite! will have in their university and in the European higher-education landscape, emphasise their key role in the co-creation of Unite!, inform them about the university transformation in the R&I dimension, strengthen the alliance's capacity for communication and dissemination.

o External Ecosystem

Unite! Satellites (stakeholders) are composed of the groups that, while not being active agents of the project, are equally important as part of the Unite! universe. Their implication can have a great impact on the development of Unite! in different ways, which is why they must be kept informed and satisfied:

Non-partner Universities and other EUI alliances

In order to transfer the best practices and recommendations arisen from the UNITE.H2020 project and Unite! E+ and thus pave the way for an Institutional transformation it is also relevant to engage, for possible synergies, universities that are not directly linked to the Unite! alliance nor part of other European University alliances. This will be fundamental in particular for UNITE.H2020 for

communicating and disseminating the R&I Agenda developed in WP2 as well as the outcomes of other work packages aimed at empowering the Universities alliances ecosystem.

Specific goal: Spreading successful practices and cooperation models will ensure that lessons learnt so that benefits will not be limited to the Unite! alliance alone.

Policy makers

European, regional and local authorities, institutions, funding bodies and other policy makers are fundamental for the project's success and sustainability, as they oversee the definition of the relevant strategies and policies for financing innovative initiatives and organisations. As one of the first 17 alliances of the European Universities Initiative, Unite! has the potential to act as a model of good practice (mainly in EU but also beyond), towards the achievement of the policy objectives of the European Education and Research Area. By influencing policy and practice we may be able to embed results in institutional strategies, training and educational practices as well as R&I strategies of relevant organizations, therefore securing their longevity.

Specific goal: consolidate a line of information to visualize the progress and results of the projects and its implications for European universities, especially as a revolution in engineering education and research; strengthen the alliance's capacity for communication and dissemination. Report and disseminate the results of the project.

Industrial and companies

Our mission as entrepreneurial European universities is predestined to help regions to execute their economic priorities and to directly promote our researchers/students/alumni for the regional industry, contributing to an overall competitiveness of Europe.

Specific goal: reinforce local, national and international relations between the project and its networks, present the projects to companies as a framework for promoting international transfer, identify the project as an internationalization attribute in communication with future client companies, strengthen the alliance's capacity for communication and dissemination.

Unite! Public (citizens and media)

Unite! Public represents the last and most external target audience of Unite! alliance. Societal engagement is a priority and responsibility of any public institution, but more so for the Unite! partner universities, given their high impact on society at all levels (education, research, industry, etc.). It requires selected products and channels in order to reach it.

Prospective students: our youngest play a big role in shaping the future of European universities and global higher education and research, and it is essential to capture their attention so they can become the next Unite! Generation of students and researchers, thus ensuring a future for Unite! as a University of the Future.

Specific goal: introduce the network as an internationalization agent that will achieve a pan-European university. For each institution, Unite! will be instrumental for attracting talented students and PhDs. Emphasise the benefits and career development opportunities (outside and/or inside the university, as a researcher) of studying in a Unite! university, emphasise their potential role in Unite! as a bottom-up network.

Schools and families: the key to consolidate our future students.

Specific goal: inform them of what Unite! is, communicate results and emphasise the benefits of Unite! as an alliance of technical universities

Media communications

Pivotal audience and channel of the communication of Unite!'s projects development and results, the visibility of the alliance, and the establishment of the brand. This includes local and international press, as well as specialised journalists, communication and outreach associations, and international relations. The relationship with the media is assumed by the organization of an event. The WP9 UNITE.H2020 and TF10 Unite! E+ will supervise the contents and the branding, and assume the preparation of other

materials outside the events (before or later). Furthermore it will take the responsibility to segment opinion leaders and potential customers among which the project or event will be disseminated.

Specific goal: to socially project the Unite! alliance to reach wide general audiences, especially for determinate projects, present the project with the aspirational 'Pan-European University of Engineering', identify Unite! as a stir in engineering training, identify the project as the European transfer project, involve specialized journalists and spread through specialized channels, provide them with clear and efficient materials and indications for the communication/dissemination of Unite!, strengthen the alliance's capacity for communication and dissemination.

2.4.2 Influence environment

In order to determine the best approach for UNITE.H2020 and Unite! E+ projects, we will take advantage of the pilot phase to identify the project's **influence environment and relations with the mass media** in a map. The mapping of stakeholders drawn by WP4, in collaboration with WP7 and WP2, will be used as the basis for a properly oriented dissemination strategy. Each stakeholder will be categorized communication wise by using appropriate variables defining the level of engagement with Unite!, which will help defining the most adequate and efficient channel, material, frequency and message for each stakeholder in order to maintain and/or increase their engagement.

Furthermore, each university will be asked to act as a multiplier of the impact on their environment and among its network. Partners will be encouraged to identify their influence environments and build up their own network relations with local partners and enterprises, as well as influential channels and opinion leaders, including academic staff, students in representative positions, press and other media.

This map will be developed during the pilot project, and it will come in handy for future Unite! alliance activities.

2.5. Communication channels

2.5.1. Internal channels (Unite! ecosystem)

For internal communication purpose both Unite! E+ and Unite.H2020 projects share the following internal channels:

uShare

Used as a communication channel and document repository. It is the main channel for internal communication. There are multiple communities (per TF, per WP, per event, circumstantial - e.g. Covid-19 dedicated community-, etc.). This goes along with the three perspectives of internal communication described in the audience classification above. TFCs have owner status to allow more flexibility. UShare comprehends UNITE.H2020 dedicated sections and folders.

Internal newsletter (Unite! brief)

The internal newsletter is a strategic product of the Unite! alliance, aimed at informing the Unite! community. It is managed by the secretariat of the alliance and it is sent on a quarterly basis. The contents include an update of the Unite! alliance's projects progress as a whole: general Unite! updates, UNITE.H2020 WP updates and Unite! E+ TF updates, quotables (selection of quotes as feedback or for promotion) and featured information. UNITE.H2020 project has specific highlights and news about its progress and related issues.

This is also useful for reporting as well as for pooling outreach content and material. The internal newsletter will be used to determine the contents for the external newsletter.

The first newsletter was sent in late 2020 and will continue until the end of the pilot projects (October 2023).

2.5.2. External channels (Partners' and external ecosystems)

Metacampus for Unite! (M4U)

The [Unite! Metacampus](#) (M4U) is a digital platform that connects the seven universities of the alliance, to enable mobile access exclusively to the range of programmes and diversity of activities that are offered through Unite!. It is addressed to the partner ecosystem, to allow access to Unite! contents and events for all staff and students within the alliance. It will be used to promote UNITE.H2020 activities and events to the Unite! and partner ecosystems.

Unite! Website

UNITE.H2020 was included in the www.unite-university.eu website established when the Unite! E+ was financed. This website is the main Unite! alliance's reference, and as such, it articulates the information for general audiences of the project. It is conceived as a repository for information materials and it includes all publishable project outcomes. Its ever-evolving development answers to the positioning of the Unite! alliance growth. The homepage is the most dynamic page of the public part of the website. In order to account for the variety of our audience, the language of the website news will have an institutional tone, focusing on communicative pragmatism and following the standard editorial guidelines, while also using more informal registers to ease reading. [UNITE.H2020](#) has a specific section, as the Unite! E+ has, describing each of the WPs where updating progresses of their work is described.

List of purchased Unite! website domains:

unite-university.eu; unite-university.cat; unite-university.com; unite-university.es; unite-university.net; unite-university.org

Linking Websites

Every partner created a section or a dedicated page in their official university's website that introduces the university as a Unite! partner, stating their involvement in the consortium. The goal of this page is to provide information that is locally relevant, as well as to show the diverse and multilingual reality of the Unite! alliance. e.g. <https://www.polito.it/international/unite/index.php?lang=en>. UNITE.H2020 is also detailed in the dedicated linking pages.

Social media networks

In addition to the Unite! alliance website, UNITE.H2020 will benefit from Unite! alliance social media, used to communicate/ disseminate events and achievements, as well as to promote discussions and engage the different Unite! alliance audiences. Social networks are useful tools for establishing a continuous interaction with project stakeholders, for keeping daily interest towards project initiatives and events and for sharing key achievements. The investment is low and the social impact is very high, reaching an EU and global scope in a very short time, within reasonable costs.

An analysis of the audience feedback will allow the adjustment of the communication strategy accordingly. All social media will be connected to each other, as well as to the website, and links will be visible and easily accessible to stimulate interaction and views.

The main objectives of the Unite! alliance social media accounts are:

- Spreading project information, activities and results
- Expanding the outreach of Unite!
- Allowing the creation of a very interactive communication
- Attracting talent and quality subscriptions
- Generating and sharing quality content

The Unite! alliance social media accounts will expand its contents and targets for UNITE.H2020 project which will leverage on and will benefit from the following accounts:

The Twitter account of Unite! alliance, [@Unite_tech_univ](#), will be used as the closest public channel to Unite! Audiences of both projects (Unite! E+ and UNITE.H2020), which is why an informal tone will be used. It aims at being an updated information source, as well as a networking platform. In terms of frequency, quality will be prioritised over quantity. The twitter will be updated adhoc with selected information about UNITE.H2020 and Unite!E+ as well as taking advantage of external information when there's no Unite! exclusive content. Some tweets will be shared in their original language to attract a diverse audience that reflects the Unite! alliance multilingual reality.

Main tags used, as agreed by the Unite! partners: #LetsUnite, #EuropeanUniversities, #UniteH2020.

Main accounts to be tagged: @TUDarmstadt @AaltoUniversity @RI_GrenobleINP @KTHuniversity @PoliTOnews @ULisboa @la_UPC

Other accounts of interest: @EU_Comission, @EUErasmusPlus, @euatweets (European University Association), ESNA (European higher education News), other European University alliances (@charm_eu, @EC2U_alliance, @allianceYufe, @EDUCUniverCity, @YERUN_EU, @CIVICA_EU, @euhalliance...), network partners, etc. To be further delimited in the deployment of the project.

YouTube channel

The alliance YouTube channel [Unite! Technological Universities' alliance](#) will collect all the contents related to Unite E+ project and UNITE.H2020 project. The purpose of the YouTube channel is acting as the nucleus for multimedia references, making them easily accessible and shareable. The YouTube channel includes: basic Unite! alliance information; links to website and Twitter; Unite! video repository. A [video manual](#) has been created to aid the partners in the branding process of the videos.

Special attention will be paid to the use of keywords and hashtags: #LetsUnite, #EuropeanUniversities, #Innovation, #Technology, #Engineering.

Additional social media channels for specific audiences (e.g. LinkedIn) will be evaluated based on feasibility analysis.

External Newsletter (Unite! Bite)

An online newsletter is an effective way to keep interested parties informed about the project's progress, achieved results and relevant events at local and international level. The main channel of distribution will be the partner network of contacts and the different distribution lists Unite! alliance has access to. The main goal will be to spotlight the Unite!E+ and Unite.H2020 projects and their main initiatives to a large interested audience, as well as positioning the different Unite! alliance products among the selected target audiences. While the newsletter registration will be open to anyone, the contents will be addressed primarily to the Unite! alliance community. The newsletter will include:

- Basic information about the project.
- Update on Unite! Products.
- Key results
- Past events' feedback and future events to be promoted.
- Contacts and useful resources.

Registration to the newsletter should be encouraged in Unite! alliance events and whenever possible. It will be available through Unite! alliance' s website. The newsletter's branding will be designed with a branding agency.

European Commission (EC) channels

Besides being the main funding body of Unite! alliance the EC counts with highly active channels with a big audience. Taking advantage of these channels doesn't only comply with the reporting obligation as

an Erasmus+ and H2020 programmes beneficiaries, but it also gives Unite! alliance access to their audiences, which can have great benefits in terms of scope and engagement. Relevant EC channels to promote the Unite! alliance products will be perhaps the [CORDIS](#) and specifically for UNITE.2020 the news [Horizon Results Platform](#).

Partner-specific communication channels

In addition to the project and EC channels each partner will echo projects results through their local communication resources: magazines, internal newsletters (general and audience-specific: for students, administration, teachers, researchers...), etc.

2.6. Materials

UNITE.H2020 will leverage on multiple materials created for the Unite! alliance, designed to fulfil its communication objectives and achieve the best results. The SCT will oversee the general Unite! alliance communication materials and UNITE.H2020, as the Unite!E+ project, will benefit from dedicated materials.

2.6.1. Internal resources

SCT communication protocol. The communication plan will include a protocol for the communication, planning and implementation of Unite! alliance activities, workshops and promotional campaigns. Each organizer of an event or workshop will be able to refer to a series of well-defined items on how to design a program for the event in line with the Unite! alliance brand. This also becomes a promotional concept for high quality management of events.

- **Templates.** UNITE.H2020 will have specific multiple templates in different formats based on those prepared for the Unite! alliance in order to assist the partners in creating corporative Unite! alliance materials, and uploaded to the uShare community. Mainly:
 - basic word corporate template
 - basic pptx corporate template
 - image consent form
 - press release template
- **Manuals.** UNITE.H2020 will refer to the manuals and communication guidelines made available to help all Unite! alliance partners incorporate the Unite!'s brand, thus unifying its portrayal in different media. Namely, a [brand manual](#), a [video editing manual](#) and graphic guidelines for different formats: leaflets, articles, etc (to be developed).
- **Other materials.** UNITE.H2020 will have other materials designed and made available to respond to specific needs, for example a promotional package including a basic presentation of the Unite! alliance and UNITE.H2020 project for different uses, or an infographic to be printed as poster.

2.6.2. Communication material

UNITE.H2020 project will refer to the commitment of the Unite! alliance to make the diversity of the alliance as visible as possible. In all Unite! alliance materials, we will include individuals and themes promoting diverse abilities and capabilities, ethnicities, religions, social and cultural worldviews and gender balance to welcome everyone interested in Unite!. They will be mainly developed in English, although translations will be evaluated for cases in which there's a strong local or regional component or impact. In that case, the local partner should aid in the translation of the materials. UNITE.H2020 project will use the following materials to promote its outcomes:

- **Press releases.** For key events or achievements, press releases will be created and disseminated within project-partner and external networks. A press release template will be made available on UShare.

- **Graphic materials.** Multiple graphic materials have been designed for the Unite! alliance and to complement materials for events. UNITE.H2020 project will have adapted versions of Unite! presentation infographic, adhoc figures, a rollout, etc.
- **Pictures.** Where the existing photos of partners fit they should be used. Our regions, cities and landscapes are certainly an asset we would like to show. i.e. Pictures of campuses or the city. A picture repository is available in our internal platform (Ushare) with the pictures that partners make available for general Unite! use and promotion.
- **Videos.** Videos are a very attractive and effective communication medium for specific messages. Videos will be created for different events and milestones in order to stimulate their promotion and reach a wider audience. Short recordings of representative moments of some events can aid promotion through SSMM and the website.
- **Other materials.** Different materials from the ones above will be explored in order to communicate the content in the most efficient format. This will include materials like blog entries for the website (e.g. Covid-19 actions within Unite! alliance), reviews (e.g. publishing feedback or results from an event), etc.

2.7. Contents

Multiple possibilities will be explored to expand the interaction between all the target audiences, taking advantage of all Unite! alliance channels and the network. The contents will be offered in a format that complies with the values and attributes of Unite! alliance and its specific projects (see 2.3.1. project identity)

UNITE.H2020 contents will be part of the broad framework of the Unite! alliance which will have four levels of contents's scope, ordered by relevance:

- **Unite! alliance.** Main content for most Unite! alliance materials and channels. The website, and YouTube content will be kept Unite!-exclusive. This content may include:
 - General Unite! alliance information
 - Results and impact
 - Key upcoming events
 - Project milestones
 - Unite! products progress, launch and calls-of-action (Virtual Campus, Mobility4All, etc.)
- **Specific UNITE.H2020 and Unite!E+ project news.** This news will be mainly:
 - General project information
 - Results and impact
 - Key upcoming events
 - Project milestones
- **Partner-exclusive selected news**, which may not be related to Unite! (relevant events, awards, new grants, etc.). Interesting for twitter and occasionally for the website (e.g. [new ERC grants to Unite! partners](#)).
- **Other information of interest** (relevant EU news, relevant higher education and R&I news, other alliances' information of interest, etc.). While the focus will be on the Unite! alliance and its partners, there are many advantages to also sharing selected information from other sources, which could be of interest to the Unite! audiences. This is especially interesting for Twitter. There are three main benefits to include some degree of external information:
 - Adaptation. It displays a real effort when adapting to our audiences' interests, as well as solidarity to sister alliances and other related entities.
 - Growth. It can increase the scope of the account by accessing new audiences.

- Consolidation. It establishes the channel as a relevant source of information about Unite! and related topics.

All of this translates into quality subscriptions, high engagement and audience fidelity.

2.8. Implementation plan

Starting from the revision of the internal Communication Plan of the Unite! alliance additional activities have been planned specifically for the UNITE.H2020 project Communication Plan Implementation. The table below show how the Unite! alliance communication channels (see 2.5), updated and enhanced to properly communicate the UNITE.H2020 project, will be used to inform the identified target audiences (see.2.4) about the project results and outcomes.

Activity	Purpose	Audience	When	Indicators of success
Public website	The Unite! alliance website will be the main channel for information on UNITE.H2020 and will aim to reach all of the project's audiences through targeted communication material.	All target groups	M1 The UNITE.H2020 website will act as main channel and it will be connected with the Unite! alliance website	At least 50 000 views from 15 countries
Social media	UNITE.H2020 will rely on Unite! alliance Twitter account @Unite_tech_univ to highlight project's news and actions undertaken and engage in a two-way dialogue with the audience	All target groups	M1-M36	Number of views, group members etc.
E-newsletters	UNITE.H2020 will have a dedicated section in at least 3 issues of the Unite! alliance external e-newsletter (see. 2.5.2) to spotlight the project and its main initiatives	All target groups	M6, M18, M30	Number of subscribers
Publications and press relations	3 press releases will be done: the first will be issued at the launch of the project, one in the second half of project life and the last one will highlight the project's results. At least 3 articles will be published in mainstream journals and specialized magazines.	All target groups	M1, M12, M20, M24, M30, M36	At least 5 mentions of the project in the media
Outreach events	UNITE.H2020 will participate to the following events: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Researchers' night or local science festivals organized by each partner (e.g., POLITO Biennale 	Citizens and students		Number of subscribers

	<p>Tecnologia https://www.biennaletecnologia.it/),</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open lab days during which local audience visits the labs to experience in vivo how research is carried out at the local university, • Open days where is given to future applicants an insight into what it's like to study at the Universities involved in the project, where the concept of a new European University will be communicated and diffused 			
<p>Project and dissemination events</p>	<p>UNITE.H2020 will organize and participate to other workshops and events with a dissemination purpose which will be specifically described in the Dissemination Plan (M18) as they will be channels to transfer specific results and outcomes to the stakeholders of the project with a co-creative approach. Some examples of planned workshop and events are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project workshops: Unite! HRS4R workshop (WP5); Co-creation workshop (WP6); workshop launching the white paper on societal outreach and citizens involvement (WP7); two matchmaking workshops with other alliance(s) or groups of alliances two collaborative matchmaking workshops (WP8). • Academia-business cooperation events: SLUSH (www.slush.org), • R&I for a: Euro Science Open Forum (https://www.esof.eu/en/), the European Regions Research and Innovation Network ERRIN events (https://errin.eu/events/european-research-and-innovation-days-2020), conferences of the European community of Research Managers and Administrators EARMA (https://www.earmaconference.com/), conferences organized by networks such as CESAER and EUA of which the Unite H2020 are active members and finally, the Forum of European Universities (FOREU) 	<p>Universities, Policy makers, companies, other alliances</p>	<p>M3-M12-M36</p>	<p>Number of participants</p>

3. Reporting communication and sustainability

3.1 Reporting

Monitoring and keeping track of the outcomes and outreach of the communication activities is crucial for the consortium to be able to evaluate the effectiveness of the communication strategy, as well as a compulsory responsibility towards reporting to the European Commission. For this purpose, a communication report has been created. It includes the main information on communication and dissemination activities as well as a section to provide evidence of the event.

The communication report includes any dissemination or communication activity, event, conference or meeting, which UNITE.H2020 organises or participates in. This also may include UNITE.H2020 partners participating in external events, meetings with stakeholders, press releases and media appearances.

3.2 Sustainability

Sustainability is the capacity of the Unite! alliance to continue to exist and function beyond the formal end of the project. UNITE.H2020 as well as Unite!E+ projects will support their sustainable and long-term activities in order to ensure a continuum of communication & dissemination also beyond 2025. The ambition is, thanks to feedback, iteration and interventions, to generate a platform to answer to the needs of all key agents and audiences of Unite!. This will ensure maximum support for all pilot activities during 2019-2025, especially targeting and supporting the work of individuals involved in the activities of the work packages.

The sustainable development of Unite! alliance is not only dependent on the products (UNITE.H2020 R&I Agenda, UNITE.H2020 Human capital strategy, Unite!E+ Virtual Campus, etc.). It must also fundamentally be linked to the development of solid partnerships and relations between Unite! alliance partners and all the relevant stakeholders or networks that could help to maintain or expand the outputs of the project after it ends. The sustainability of Unite! alliance will be ensured by strong cooperation not only in the academic spheres and its networks but also with policy makers at local, regional and national level. The Alumni Ambassadors Programme will be another focus to ensure the sustainability of the alliance.

4. Other considerations

4.1. Risk Assessment

In line with the UNITE.H2020 Grant Agreement and in particular with table 1.3.5. Critical Implementation risks and mitigation actions (p.106) following is the specific risk assessment table related to WP9.

Risk number	Description of risk	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
3	imperfect alignment with Unite!E+	Other than KLO, each WP needs to be fully aware of Unite!E+ plans and state of the activities indicate level of likelihood: Low
9	Delay in defining a common communication strategy	The communication strategy developed within Unite! E+ as well as communication processes defined within the Unite! community are a solid basis to build on. A well-balanced communication strategy that links Unite! E+ and UNITE.H2020 to their best purpose will be ensured by the internal management processes. Furthermore, the continuous iteration among WPs by meetings of WPL will be strengthened to align messages (see management structure H2020 project). level of likelihood: high
10	Delay in mapping stakeholders to define a specific communication strategy	A strong link between WP4 and WP9 is sought after by WPL from the beginning, so that a timely and agile adaptation and integration into the communication strategy is possible. Interactive feedback loops will be used to develop the multipurpose vision of the map. level of likelihood: medium
11	Delay in designing a dissemination strategy	As the dissemination strategy relies on the output of all WPs internal communication within the UNITE.H2020 community is key. Linking the WPL within the management structure ensures that. level of likelihood: medium
13	Working balance and healthy work environment	Working balance and healthy work environment

